

ELECTRICAL SYSTEM ASSESSMENT OF BOARDING HOUSES IN UNIVERSITY OF EASTERN PHILIPPINES-MAIN CAMPUS: COMPLIANCE TO PHILIPPINE ELECTRICAL CODE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the level of compliance of the electrical system of boarding houses in the University of Eastern Philippines by determining the profile, degree of compliance to the Philippine Electrical Code, malpractices and the percentage of the feeder and main spare capacity of future loads. This study utilized descriptive-evaluative-survey design. Findings revealed that majority of boarding house owners were college graduates, boarding houses were 10 years old and below and were only inspected once or very frequent, and the board houses were just started operating and accepting boarders for 5 years or just a few years ago and is mostly new in business. Compliance rating for light and switches of boarding houses was 71.1%, for receptacle outlets were 40.5%, for panel boards were 35.5%, for feeders were 57.5%, for service entrance of 35.4%. 7.5% of the boarding houses have a motor loads, 33.3% boarding houses complied to the requirement specified in the PEC. Therefore, none of the boarding houses are compliant to PEC. Malpractices was identified which includes the electrical system that were installed not properly tightened and neatly arranged, not protected against penetration and abrasion, and most conductors were not color coded.

Keywords: Compliance, feeder capacity, malpractice, Philippine Electrical Code, profile

I. INTRODUCTION

In our daily lives there is a greater need of electricity. Without it, many things will be affected including works or even simple activities that requires the use of such. There is a greater need of huge amount of electricity required in various aspects of our lives that is why several ideas were adopted to produce

electricity (Markandya and Wilkinson, 2007). With improper installations and use of electricity, high rate of devastating events may occur.

In the study of Dyško & Tzelepis (2022), they revealed that one of the crucial areas that is commonly disregarded is power system

protection, which is a safety-critical element of all electrical systems. The preservation of system integrity and the mitigation of the potential adverse effects on the rest of the grid are facilitated by the timely and accurate identification and removal of malfunctioning components, as well as the fast and reliable detection of abnormal circumstances. The ramifications of a significant blackout in the transmission system are unimaginably dire.

Boarding houses are necessary for students especially to those who lived in far places. Several of these boarding houses are powered with electrical energy (Nobis, 2022). However, home electrical safety is too important to ignore considering the hazards that may bring due to an unsafe practices of installation.

Accidental house fires cause fatalities and damage to property. Residential fires can be started by electrical faults, which provide a higher risk as more electrical gadgets are now located in every housing unit. Wiring has a larger chance of igniting (Lovitos, 2019). Based on the secondary data from the BFP Catarman of Northern Samar, there are thirty-five (35) cases of fire incidents from January 2017 up to present in Catarman, Northern Samar and twenty-seven (27) of these reported cases were caused by electrical systems. In January 16, 24, and June 23, 2017, there are reported fire incidents cause of electrical short circuit in Brgy. Zone III, UEP, Purok 1, Brgy. Dalakit, and Jacinto St. Brgy. Molave, costing one million (1M) pesos, three hundred forty-five thousand and five hundred fifty (345,550.00) pesos, and one-million and five hundred thousand (1.5M) pesos consecutively in damage to property. In July 1, 2017, another fire incident happened in G.H. Del Pilar St. Brgy. Casoy cause of overheated electrical appliance and a damage to property worth of three hundred thousand (300,000) pesos. Another cause of short circuit happened on September 25, 2017 at Purok 4, Brgy. Baybay. In October 2, 2017, the cause of fire in Sto. Tara, Purok 1, Brgy. Dalakit is overheated electrical appliance and electrical short circuit in Purok 6, Brgy. Baybay on December 16, 2017. It is the last reported fire incident during the year.

In 2018, from February to October, there were seven (7) reported fire incidents in municipality of Catarman and six (6) of these incidents were caused by electrical short circuit, and the other was caused by overheated defective Electrical appliance. In the year 2019, There were six (6)

reported fire incidents and three (3) of these were caused by electrical short circuit, two (2) electrical ignitions caused by overloading, and ignition materials caused by welding slags. Moreover, on September 12, 2020, a fire incident happened at Bonifacio St. Brgy. Santol with a damage to property worth of one-million and two hundred thousand (1.2M) pesos cause of electrical ignition due to pinched wire. In January 31, 2021 at National Highway, Brgy. Old Rizal, a residential establishment, electrical short circuit due to overheated outlet with plugged substandard fan happened in electrical outlet located at the room of occupant with a cost estimate of six hundred and ten thousand (610,000) pesos damage to property. In addition, on March 25 of the same year at Upper hillside, Purok 5, Brgy. UEP zone II, another residential establishment caught on fire due to electrical ignition caused by arcing in electrical lighting outlet located at the second floor of Maceriano Residence with a damage to property worth of one million and five hundred thousand (1.5M) pesos.

In the present year (2022), there were a total of five (5) fire incidents in Catarman, Northern Samar. The first case happened in a two-storey residential family dwelling on January 30, 2022 at Purok 2, Brgy. Yakal. The cause of fire was electrical ignition caused by overloading at the second floor, left wing bedroom of the building. Another fire incident in a two-storey residential family dwelling at Brgy. Talisay on May 2, 2022 happened with a cause of overheated home appliance, specifically a ceiling fan attached to the ceiling of second floor. Moreover, on September 12, 2022 at Bonifacio St. Brgy. Mabolo, an electrical junction box located at the second floor were electrically ignite caused by arcing at the junction box. In addition, two fire incidents were reported at same date in a two different location, Purok 5, Brgy. Macagtas and Maharlika Highway, Brgy UEP, ZONE II, on October 27, 2022. Both buildings were mixed occupancy. The cause of fire in the first building is electrical ignition due to pinched wire that happened at the wooden post located at the parking and the latter is caused by electrical ignition due to arcing on the third floor Saturnino Store (BFP Catarman).

This study, therefore, assessed and evaluated the electrical system of boarding houses in the University of Eastern Philippines. By this, electrical systems were examined as a preventive measure from electrical hazards and as a possible precursor to a regular monitoring, in promoting compliance of the

Philippine Electrical Code by these boarding houses.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study utilized descriptive-evaluative-survey design as it evaluates the degree of compliance to 2017 Philippine Electrical Code of the components/devices of the electrical systems of boarding houses in the University of Eastern Philippines. It also assessed the electrical facilities and conduct survey of building construction. This method of research was an appropriate design in finding out the present existing condition.

Population and Sampling Technique. This study was conducted in the boarding houses of University of Eastern Philippines. At present, there were 165 registered boarding houses in the University town. To complete the 80 boarding houses, the researchers have inspected boarding houses that were not even included in the list given from Office of Student Affairs (OSA). That was for a reason that the list was not updated and most of the boarding houses listed was not existing anymore and has already stopped operating.

The sampling technique that the researchers used was random sampling method. Sampling from the population was often more practical and allows data to be collected faster and at a lower cost than attempting to reach every member of the population (Turner, 2020).

Hence, by using the Slovin's formula the number of boarding houses to be assessed in this study was 80 approximately. We used 8% margin of error instead of 10 because the acceptable margin of error usually falls between 4% and 8%.

Research Instrument. Data collection instruments fell into two categories. First, the data sheet and the other one was the inspection checklist. The data sheet included a profile of the boarding houses and the boarders or tenants. The researchers have conducted interviews with the owners of the boarding houses or used credible references from the tenants. On the other hand, the inspection checklist acted as an assessment guide.

The Bureau of Fire Protection created the checklist. Furthermore, the researchers also made their own checklist to be added in the checklist of the Bureau of Fire Protection including the availability of the electrical plan for each boarding houses. These additions were intended for the needs of this study. Its foundation was the provisions in the 2017 Philippine Electrical Code, which land down the accepted and mandated standards, criteria, and specifications for building electrical systems. The inspection checklist was a brief, ordered set of the specifications used to evaluate each feature, component, and device of the electrical systems. Using this, the electrical systems of boarding houses would be evaluated for their level of conformity. In determining the demographic profile of the respondents, statistical tools such as frequency counts and percentage was used.

The researchers determined and assessed the collected data and used "compliant" and "non-compliant" in interpreting the categorizations on this study.

Data Gathering Procedure. There were 165 registered boarding houses in the University town and some of these were not operating anymore, therefore, the researchers have decided to conduct inspection to some registered and unregistered boarding houses in order complete the 80 boarding houses to be assessed. The researchers have visited every boarding houses, provided that the respective boarding houses owners have also given their permissions.

Meanwhile, the researchers interviewed the respondents to obtain data in terms of their educational attainment, age of boarding houses, frequency of inspection and the years of operation of these selected boarding houses.

In obtaining the information to the compliance of light and switches, receptacle outlets, panel boards, feeders, service entrance and other electrical devices, the researchers have used the PEC inspection checklist.

Afterwards, the researchers inspected and evaluated the components/devices of the electrical system of the particular boarding houses and determined the malpractices in each boarding houses.

Component conducted survey on building loads by enumerating the total connected loads and determines the feeder capacity and its allowance for future loads. The ampacity of the feeder was determined in the Article 3.10.2.6 table (B)(16) and to calculate the total connected loads the researchers apply the demand factor as shown in the Article 3.10.3.3 table A in the Philippine Electrical Code. The data then will be recorded.

Data Analysis Procedure. The analysis of the data was based on the following categorization. Part I of the study questionnaire pertains to the profile of respondents and boarding houses. The educational attainment of the respondents, age of boarding houses, frequency of inspection and number of years of operation were interpreted using frequency counts and percentage.

As to the electrical system, the researchers determined the components and devices if it was compliant or not.

This study adopted the description below, which was more definite and categorical:

Compliant - The unit was totally conforming to the PEC's prescribed standard/specification indicated on the checklist's inspection item.

Non-compliant - The unit conforms with the PEC's prescribed standard/specification indicated on the checklist's inspection item. One violation would be automatically considered not compliant.

Portion of the unit follows the prescribed standard/ specification indicated on the inspection checklist.

Meanwhile, the mean which represented the overall compliance rating of a particular boarding houses, derived by adding the entire mean of the ratings of all the types of devices/components of the boarding houses' electrical system and dividing the result by the total number of types of components/devices.

Statistical Treatment of Data. The gathered data were analyzed using the following statistical tools:

Weighted Mean (Mean). The computation of the weighted mean was the key to determining the —degree of compliance to PEC. This formula was applied in computing the mean of the following:

a. The degree of compliance to the PEC of each type of component/device found in a particular section of the boarding house, derived by summing up the mean of its ratings in all of the inspection items and dividing it by the total number of items.

b. The degree of compliance to the PEC of each type of component/device of an electrical system (boarding house), derived by summing up the entire mean of the overall ratings of the particular type of component/device in the different sections of boarding house and dividing it by the total number of sections containing such type of component/device.

The degree of compliance to the PEC of a particular boarding house, derived by adding the entire mean of the ratings of all the types of devices/components of the boarding house's electrical system and dividing it by the total number of types of devices/components.

The degree of compliance to the PEC of boarding houses as a whole, which was computed by adding the entire mean of the compliance ratings of all the assessed boarding houses and dividing the result by the total number of assessed boarding houses (eighty (80) in all).

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

Where: \bar{X} = mean
 $\sum x$ = summation of the value of observation
 n = total number of cases

For the malpractices, the researchers had inspected the electrical system of boarding houses, assessed and analyzed the current situation of their electrical system. Meanwhile, the ampacity of the feeder was determined in the Article 3.10.2.6 table (B)(16) and to calculate the total connected loads the researchers apply the demand factor as shown in the Article 3.10.3.3 table A in the Philippine Electrical Code (PEC 2017).

III. RESULTS

Profile of Boarding Houses

Educational Attainment. Table 1 showed that 53 out of 80 boarding house owners were college graduate. They represent 66.25% of all respondents. 14 or 17.5% were college level. 12 or 15% of the respondents were high school graduate, and 1 or 1.25% out of 80 respondents was an elementary graduate, representing smallest percentage of the total respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents according to their Educational attainment

Distance	Frequency	Percentage
College Graduate	53	66.25%
College Level	14	17.5%
High School Graduate	12	15%
High School Level	0	0%
Elementary Graduate	1	1.25%
Elementary Level	0	0%

Age of Boarding Houses. Table 2 showed that out of 80 boarding houses, 50 of these were

built 10 years and below or 62.5% among all the boarding houses. For 11 to 20 years old buildings, there were 13 or 16.25%. 4 or 5% of aged 21 to 30 years building and there were 13 or 16.25% for boarding houses that were built 31 years and above.

Table 2. Distribution of the Respondents according to the age of the boarding houses

Distance	Frequency	Percentage
10 years old and below	50	62.5%
11-20 years old	13	16.25%
21-30 years old	4	5%
31 years old and above	13	16.25%

Frequency of Inspection. Table 3 showed that most of these boarding houses were only inspected once or very frequent. Owners that have their boarding houses inspected once was 52 or 65% out of 80 boarding houses, 22 or 27.5% were inspected twice or thrice and those 11 houses or 13.75% have inspection for their electrical system for already more than 3 times.

Table 3. Distribution of the Respondents according to Frequency of Inspection

Frequency of Inspection	Frequency	Percentage
1	52	65%
2-3	22	27.5%
More than 3	11	13.75%

Number of Years Operation of Boarding Houses. Table 4 showed that the boarding houses operating for 5 years and below got a total of 42 or 52.5% out of 80 boarding houses in the University of Eastern Philippines-main campus. 16 or 20% boarding houses operating for 6 to 10 years. 4 or 5% of the total boarding houses who were operating for already 11 to 15 years. In 16 to 20-year operation there are 2 or 2.5% representing the smallest percentage of the total boarding houses. 4 or 5% of the total boarding houses who were operating for already 16 to 20 years. Lastly, there were 12 or 15% of the total boarding houses operating for 26 years and above.

Table 4. Distribution of the Respondents according to Frequency of Inspection

Years	Frequency	Percentage
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5 Years and below	42	52.5%
6-10 years	16	20%
11-15 years	4	5%
16-20 years	2	2.5%
21-25 years	4	5%
26 years and above	12	15%

Degree of Compliance to The Philippine Electrical Code

As shown in Table 5, the compliant rating for light and switches of boarding houses was 71.1% while not compliant was 28.9%, for receptacle outlets was 40.5% of boarding houses that were compliant and 59.5% not compliant, there were 35.5% compliant and 64.5% not compliant rating in terms of panel boards, there were 57.5% compliant and 42.5% not compliant in terms of feeder, most boarding houses' electrical system were not compliant in terms of service entrance. It garnered only 35.4% compliant and 64.6% not compliant, and out of 80 boarding houses, there were only 6 boarding houses that have a motor loads. 2 out of 6 or 33.3% boarding houses complied to the requirement specified in the PEC and 4 or 66.66% were not compliant.

Table 5. Distribution of the Degree of Compliance to PEC

Electrical Devices	Percentage	
	Compliant	Non-compliant
Light and Switches	71.1%	28.9%
Receptacle Outlets	40.5%	59.5%
Panel boards	35.5%	64.5%
Feeder	57.5%	42.5%
Service Entrance	35.4%	64.6%
Other Electrical Devices	33.3%	66.66%

Non-Compliance and Malpractices of Boarding Houses

In most boarding houses, the researchers have observed that some of conductors for L.O did not have electrical support, bulbs were hanging

and defective bulbs had not yet been replaced. Also, lamp holder was tapped outside the junction box and was not properly tightened, some junction boxes were not covered and did not have proper fittings. Conductors were not protected against nicks and abrasion and were not color coded, conduits were not reamed and trimmed and there were excess of wires in conduits.

The researchers have found out that there were splices outside the junction boxes and conductors were not color coded. Some were not properly tightened and CO were not protected against abrasion.

It was observed that wires were not color coded and most conduits entering the main panel board in the entrances were not neatly arranged, not reamed properly and did not conform to the standard height. Some conductors were not functional and most panel boards did not have labeling or directory.

Feeders were not neatly arranged and not protected against penetration from damage.

Service entrance in most boarding houses did not have drip loop and a service entrance cap. Some hang their service entrance in a steel bar.

Capacity of Feeder and its allowance for Future Loads

The Ampacity of the feeder was determined in the Article 3.10.2.6 table (B)(16) and to calculate the total connected loads the researchers applied the demand factor as shown in the Article 3.10.3.3 table A in the Philippine Electrical Code. Shown in table 6 that 1 or 1.25% out of 80 boarding houses has a feeder size of 14mm² having a load of 16860VA plus 1 hp motor, 230 V nominal and the total ampere of 44.13. Since the ampacity of 14 mm² was 75 A, 58.84% of the ampacity of the feeder was utilize and the load allowance was 41.16%. 12 or 15% out of 80 boarding house using 8.0 mm² feeder having a load ranges from 1138.5 to 7084 VA, 230 V nominal and total ampere ranges from 4.95 to 30.8 A. The ampacity of 8.0 mm² is 55 A, 9% to 56% of the ampacity of the feeder was utilized and having an allowance of 44% to 81% or 24.8 to 50.05 A. For boarding houses that uses a size of feeder of 5.5 mm², there were 64 out of 80 or 80% indicating load capacity ranges 1449 to 3864 VA. The 5.5 mm² feeder have an ampacity of 35A, 6.3 to 16.8 A or 18% to 48% of the ampacity was utilize and the total allowance ranges 18.2 to 28.7 A or 52% to 82%. Finally, 3 or 3.75%of boarding houses

having a feeder size of 3.5 mm² and a load ranges 39% to 60% and total allowance of 40% to 61%.

Table 6. Distribution of the Percentage of Feeder

Size of Feeder	Frequency	Percentage	Range of Percentage	Load Allowance
14 mm ²	1	1.25%	58.84%	41.16%
8.0 mm ²	12	15%	9%-56%	44%-81%
5.5 mm ²	64	80%	18%-48%	52%-82%
3.5m m ²	3	3.75%	39%-60%	40%-61%

IV. DISCUSSION

The majority of boarding house owners were college graduates as shown in Table 1. In the study of Amesi (2014), respondents indicated that educational attainment was an important critical characteristic for successful business. With regard to this, perceived that effective and successful entrepreneur, established that educational attainment was related to high-capitalization in business venturing.

Most of boarding houses were 10 years old and below as shown in Table 2. This implied that most of boarding houses were not old houses. Fragar-Approval council cited that boarding house has evolved from what we used to call boarding house. Most old boarding houses has a common room and did not have a very good reputation. On the other hand, very few boarding houses that were new built are not self-contained.

It was observed that boarding houses only have inspection when the need of inspection arises as shown in Table 3. According to Keynes (2020), while we have all become accustomed to living in an electricity-fueled world, one thing we often overlook is how safe our installations and appliances were. Electrical inspection and testing have been designed to eliminate the worry of electricity-based hazards; however, was a service that many property owners, commercial or domestic, are unfamiliar with.

It was indicated that most boarding houses in the University of Eastern Philippines just started operating and accepting boarders for 5 years or

just a few years ago and was mostly new in business as shown in Table 4.

The researchers found out that boxes in light and switches in most boarding houses were protected against corrosion, provided in every habitable room and were appropriate. Also, junction boxes in concealed locations were accessible, electrical non-metallic tubing were in a permitted location, wires were color coded, branch circuit conductors were routed in the same raceway, screw shell of lamp holders was tapped to neutral, switching was made in the underground conductors, tap conductors were sized accordingly and conductor temperature limitations were not violated. On the other hand, most boarding houses were not compliant because of rough edges that were not reamed and trimmed properly as shown in Table 5.

It was determined that boxes were in approved location and in purpose intended, and branch circuit conductors were routed in the same raceway as shown in Table 5. Likewise, most of boarding houses were not compliant with their receptacle outlets because boxes were not made of code specified materials, raceway in walled partitions were not against penetrations and not all receptacle outdoors were weatherproof type.

It was determined in most boarding houses that wires of feeder were color coded however, wire bending radius were violated as shown in Table 5.

It was observed that size and rating of service entrance were appropriate as shown in Table 5. On the other hand, rough edges were not reamed and most service entrance fails in mechanical and electrical continuity as well as in overhead service drop clearance to building openings.

V. CONCLUSION

Majority of boarding house owners were college graduates which signifies that most of boarding house owners had a good educational background. Most of boarding houses were 10 years old and below and were only inspected once, thus, the said boarding houses has deficiency when it comes on having regular inspection. Most boarding houses in the University of Eastern Philippines just started operating and accepting boarders for two years before pandemic and some boarding houses were newly built. This implied that the owners of boarding houses were considered newbies and not well experienced in such business.

None among the 80 boarding houses that the researchers have inspected were even considered compliant in terms of light and switches, receptacle outlets, panel boards, feeders, service entrance and in other electrical devices, thus, these boarding houses were prone to electrical faults which could lead to fire or electrocution.

Malpractices in most boarding houses included electrical system that were installed not properly tightened and neatly arranged, not protected against penetration and abrasion, and most conductors were not color coded.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Authors may use the following wordings for this section: " 'Author A' designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. 'Author B' and 'Author C' managed the analyses of the study. 'Author C' managed the literature searches..... All authors read and approved the final manuscript."

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